

Chelating N-ligands and their Transition Metal Complexes. Part I. Ultraviolet Absorption Spectra of *vic*- Oxime Hydrazones

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Substituted hydrazones of the derivatives of 2, 3-dioxobutyric acid 2-oxime have been prepared and their UV absorption spectra in methanol investigated.

vic-Oxime hydrazones having the structural configuration :

are expected to be closely related to *vic*-dioximes for their chelating properties; these properties, however, may be influenced by the substituents present in the hydrazone group. This might be reflected in the UV absorption spectra of these compounds. Hence, in continuation of our studies on N-ligands derived from 1,2-diketones and related substances¹, we have prepared a series of *vic*-oxime hydrazones. The present communication deals with the preparation and UV absorption spectra of the substituted hydrazones of the derivatives of 2,3-dioxobutyric acid 2-oxime (I).

Phenylhydrazones of the derivatives (namely, anilide, *N*-methylanilide, *o*-toluidide, *o*-chloroanilide, and ethyl ester) of 2,3-dioxobutyric acid 2-oxime were prepared from the corresponding derivatives of 2,3-dioxobutyric acid 2-oxime by the action of phenylhydrazine. These compounds are considered to have preferentially the *anti*-configuration (II) similar to the structure suggested for dioximes, obtained from CO-CH₂ compounds².

2, 3-Dioxo-*N*-methylbutyranilide 2-oxime methyl ether was prepared earlier and was found to contain -OMe group and not -NMe group in the methylated oxime group. This and ethyl 2,3-dioxobutyrate 2-oxime methyl ether were converted into the corresponding phenylhydrazones. On analysis, these were found to contain -OMe group as expected.

1. Talati *et al.*, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1964, **27**, 159.
2. Ishidata, *Microchim. Acta*, 1938, **3**, 203.

Introduction of methyl or chlorine in *ortho* position on the phenyl ring of the anilide also causes a blue shift of the A-band. This is attributed to the "side chain" effect of these on the conjugated system.

Methylation of the oxime group causes a blue shift of 11-12 m μ of the A-band in the case of the ester; it may be attributed to the opening up of the chelate ring involving oxime group.

The absorption spectra are different in the case of disubstituted hydrazones. Dimethyl- and diphenyl-hydrazones are considered to have different spectra; the spectrum of the methylphenylhydrazone is composite of the above two.

EXPERIMENTAL

N-Aryl-2,3-dioxobutyramide 2-oxime (where arylamide may be anilide, *N*-methyl-anilide, *o*-toluidide, and *o*-chloroanilide) and 2,3-dioxo-*N*-methylbutyranilide 2-oxime methyl ether were prepared as described earlier¹.

Phenylhydrazone of 2,3-dioxobutyranilide 2-oxime was prepared from 2,3-dioxobutyranilide 2-oxime and phenylhydrazine by the method of Knorr and Reuter³. In a similar way were prepared the phenylhydrazones of *N*-aryl-2,3-dioxobutyramide 2-oxime (where arylamide may be *N*-methylanilide, *o*-toluidide, and *o*-chloroanilide) and phenylhydrazone of 2,3-dioxo-*N*-methylbutyranilide 2-oxime methyl ether. Same method was adopted also for the preparations of dimethyl-, diphenyl- and methylphenyl-hydrazones of 2,3-dioxobutyranilide 2-oxime from 2,3-dioxobutyranilide 2-oxime and 1,1-dimethyl-, 1,1-diphenyl-, and 1-methyl-1-phenyl-hydrazine respectively.

Ethyl 2,3-dioxobutyrate 2-oxime was prepared from ethyl acetoacetate by the method of Meyer and Zublin⁴. Its phenylhydrazone was prepared by the above method.

Phenylhydrazone of Ethyl 2,3-Dioxobutyrate 2-Oxime Methyl Ether.—Anhydrous potassium carbonate (30 g.) and dimethyl sulphate (9 g.) were added to ethyl 2,3-dioxobutyrate 2-oxime (10 g.) in dry acetone and the mixture was refluxed on a water bath for about 10 hr. It was filtered, treated with NaOH to hydrolyse unchanged dimethyl sulphate, and then extracted with ether, evaporation of which left a yellow liquid. The product was converted to the phenylhydrazone by the above method. On analysis it was found to contain OMe group.

All new products were recrystallised from dilute ethanol. Colour, m.p., and analyses of these products are recorded in Table II.

UV absorption spectra of these substances in methanol were investigated with a Beckman model DU spectrophotometer, using matched 1 cm quartz cells.

3. *Ber.*, 1894, **27**, 1172.

4. *Ber.*, 1870, **11**, 322.

5. Wahl, *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1905, *iii*, **33**, 486.

Further, dimethyl-, diphenyl-, and methylphenyl-hydrazones of 2, 3-dioxobutyranilide 2-oxime were prepared by the action of 1,1-dimethyl-, 1,1-diphenyl-, and 1-methyl-1-phenyl-hydrazine, respectively, on 2,3-dioxobutyranilide 2-oxime.

Chromophore.—The intense absorption band (A) at 223-44 $m\mu$, observed in case of *vic*-oxime hydrazones (under investigation) in methanol (Table I), is considered to be a $\pi \longleftrightarrow \pi^*$ transition and is attributed to the crossed conjugated system:

Since the absorption band of 2,3-dioxobutyranilide dioxime¹ in ethanol is at 236-38 $m\mu$, the replacement of the oxime group by phenylhydrazone group causes only a small red shift of 2-4 $m\mu$. Hence it is considered that -NPh of the hydrazone increases only slightly the conjugation of crossed conjugated system, considered above.

TABLE I

UV absorption spectra in methanol.

Substance (R=).	X.	Y.	Z.	$\lambda_{\text{max.}}$ ($m\mu$)	E_m .	$\lambda_{\text{max.}}$ ($m\mu$)	E_m .	$\lambda_{\text{max.}}$ ($m\mu$)	E_m .
1 PhNH	H	Ph	H	240	20380	302 ⁺	13890	324	23590
2 o-MeC ₆ H ₄ NH	"	"	"	..	..	302 ⁺	14610	324	23740
3 o-ClC ₆ H ₄ NH	"	"	"	..	..	304 ⁺	14070	326	24560
4 PhNMe	"	"	"	..	..	304 ⁺	13400	328-30	23940
5 C ₂ H ₅ O	"	"	"	239-40	8490	302 ⁺	16050	324	24630
6 PhNMe	"	"	Me	..	..	304 ⁺	12140	332	27960
7 C ₂ H ₅ O	"	"	"	228	14140	302 ⁺	14690	330	33930
8 Ph	Me	"	H	240-42	14530	274-76	8640	316 [†]	3980
9 "	Me	Me	"	234	24350	..	..	316	4560
10 "	Ph	Ph	"	..	..	273	23360	..	..

[†] Inflection.

Besides, there is a second intense absorption band (C) at 324-34 $m\mu$ and an inflection at 302-304 $m\mu$ in the case of monosubstituted hydrazones in ethanol. The C-band may be attributed to the conjugated hydrazone system of the ligands.

Substitution Effect.—Methylation of the anilide NH- group causes a large blue shift of the A-band. This shift may result from the steric effect of the methyl group and possibly from the partial localisation of the π electrons. Alternatively, it may be attributed to the opening up of the chelate ring involving anilide.

TABLE II

*Hydrazones of the derivatives of 2,3-dioxobutyric acid 2-oxime**

*Substance. (R=)	Colour.	Melting point.		% Nitrogen.		% Methoxyl	
		Obs.	Lit.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
1 PhNH	Yellow	169°	169° ³	..	..	..	..
2 <i>o</i> -MeC ₆ H ₄ NH	Pale yellow	185°	..	18.0	18.0	..	..
3 <i>o</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄ NH	..	177°	..	16.9	17.0	..	..
4 PhNMe	..	224°	..	17.9	18.0	..	..
5 C ₂ H ₅ O	..	164°	165-66° ⁵	..	..	..	..
6 PhNMe	..	185°	..	17.9	17.3	9.63	9.57
7 C ₂ H ₅ O	..	135°	..	15.9	15.6	..	..
8 Ph	..	150°	..	18.0	18.0	..	..
9 ..	White	150°	..	22.3	22.5	..	..
10 ..	..	178°	..	15.0	15.0	..	..

*Vide structure in Table I.

N.B. X, Y, and Z are same as in Table I.

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